

Synthesis of Fused Quinazolines

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6-Bromo-2-hydrazino-3-amine-4(3*H*)-quinazolinone, 6-bromo-2-ethylamino-4*H*-3,1-benzothiazin-4-one, 9-bromo-3,4-diphenyl[1,2,4,5]-tetrazepino[3,2-*b*]quinazolin-7(1*H*)-one, 2,4-dibromo-6-methylbenzimidazo[1,2-*c*]quinazoline, 2,4-dibromo benzimidazo[1,2-*c*]quinazoline-6(5*H*)-thione, 2,4-dibromo-6-[*N,N*-benzylphenyl carbamoylmethylthio]-benzimidazo[1,2-*c*]quinazoline, *bis*-[2,4-dibromo benzimidazo[1,2-*c*]quinazolin-6-yl]-disulphide, 2,4-dibromo-6-(carboxymethylthio)-benzimidazo[1,2-*c*]quinazoline and 2,4-dibromo benzimidazo[1,2-*c*]quinazoline-6(5*H*)-one have been synthesised. Their structures have been confirmed on the basis of physico-chemical studies.

4(3*H*)-Quinazolinone derivatives possess various therapeutic activities¹⁻⁹. Keeping this in view, several thioquinazolones, substituted 3,4-diphenyl[1,2,4,5]tetrazepino[3,2-*b*]quinazolin-7(1*H*)-one, and 2,4-dibromo-6-(substituted) benzimidazo[1,2-*c*]quinazolines have been synthesised. The action of 75% conc. H₂SO₄ on 2-thio-6-bromo-3-ethyl quinazolin-2,4(1*H*,3*H*)-dione has also been investigated. The anticancer activity of these compounds is being studied at National Institute of Health and will be reported later. Several compounds have been synthesised according to Schemes 1 and 2.

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

6-Bromo-2-thio-3-*m*-chlorophenyl (or ethyl) quinazolin-2,4-(1H,3H)-diones (II) were prepared by refluxing 5-bromo anthranilic acid (I) and *m*-chlorophenyl (or ethyl) isothiocyanates in alcohol by the method of Chaurasia *et al*⁷. 6-Bromo-2-thio-3-*m*-chlorophenyl quinazolin-2,4-(1H,3H)-dione on treatment with methyl iodide in alcoholic NaOH gave III. IV was obtained by refluxing 6-bromo-2-methylthio-3-*m*-chlorophenyl 4(3H)-quinazolinone with hydrazine hydrate (60%). 9-Bromo-3,4-diphenyl-[1,2,4 5]tetrazepino[3,2-*b*]quinazolin-7(1H)-one was obtained by refluxing IV with benzil in *p*-xylene.

6-Bromo-2-thio-3-ethyl quinazolin-2,4-(1H,3H)-dione on rearrangement gave VI by the action of 75% conc. H₂SO₄. VII was obtained on refluxing 3,5-dibromo anthranilic acid and *o*-phenylenediamine in presence of PPA. 2'-[3,5-Dibromo-2-amino-phenyl]benzimidazole (VII) on refluxing with glacial acetic acid gave VIII. 2,4-Dibromo benzimidazo-[1,2-*c*]quinazolin-6(5H)-thione (IX) was obtained by refluxing VII with carbon disulphide and alcoholic KOH. When an alkaline solution of IX was treated with saturated iodine solution in KI, bis-(2,4-dibromo - benzimidazo[1,2-*c*]quinazolin-6-yl)-disulphide (XI) was obtained.

2,4-Dibromo-6-(carboxymethylthio)-benzimidazo-[1,2-*c*]quinazoline (XII) was obtained by stirring IX with sodium chloroacetate in alcoholic NaOH at room temperature. 2,4-Dibromo-6-[N,N-benzyl phenylcarbamoylmethyl thio]benzimidazo[1,2-*c*]quinazoline (X) was obtained by stirring alcoholic NaOH solution of IX with an alcoholic solution of N-benzyl chloroacetanilide. 2,4-Dibromo benzimidazo[1,2-*c*]quinazolin-6(5H)-one (XIII) was obtained by stirring XII with conc. HCl at room temperature. XIII was also obtained by the oxidation¹⁰ of IX with alkaline KMnO₄. These reactions show that alkylation occurs at the sulphur atom rather than the nitrogen atom¹¹.

Experimental

The melting points were taken in open capillary in liquid bath and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin Elmer 257 spectrophotometer. A Coleman analyser was used for elemental analysis.

5-Bromo and 3,5-dibromo anthranilic acids were prepared by known methods¹²⁻¹⁵.

6-Bromo-2-thio-3-*m*-chlorophenyl (or ethyl) quinazolin-2,4-(1H,3H)-diones (II) were prepared by the method of Bhargava *et al*⁶. IR (nujol) cm⁻¹: 3250 (m), 1715 (m), 1620 (s), 1525 (s), 1360 (s), 1135 (s), 820 (s).

6-Bromo-2-methylthio-3-*m*-chlorophenyl-4(3H)-quinazolinone (III): It was prepared by stirring II in alcoholic NaOH with methyl iodide by the method of Bhargava *et al*⁷ in 60% yield, m.p. 171° (lit. m.p. 172°). IR (nujol) cm⁻¹: 1695 (s), 1570 (m), 1540 (s), 1385 (m).

6-Bromo-2-hydrazino-3-amino-4(3H)-quinazolinone (IV)⁷: It was prepared by refluxing III (0.01 M)

in 60% hydrazine hydrate (0.02 M) for 15 hr. Excess hydrazine hydrate was distilled off. The product was washed with distilled water, dried and recrystallised from alcohol to obtain IV, yield 87%, m.p. 270°. (Found: C, 35.42; H, 2.84. Calcd. for C₈H₈BrN₅O; C, 35.56; H, 2.96%). IR (nujol) cm⁻¹: 3340 (s), 3320 (s), 3220 (m), 1740 (m), 1620 (s), 1480 (s).

9-Bromo-3,4-diphenyl[1,2,4,5]tetrazepino[3,2-*b*]quinazolin-7(1H)-one (V): IV (1 M) was dissolved in *p*-xylene (30 ml) and stirred with benzil (1 M) for 0.5 hr at room temperature and refluxed for 20 hr. Excess *p*-xylene was distilled off. The product obtained was cooled, filtered, washed with distilled water and dried. It was recrystallised from alcohol-benzene mixture (1:2) in 52% yield, m.p. 236°. (Found: C, 59.31; H, 3.07. Calcd. for C₂₃H₁₄BrN₅O; C, 59.46; H, 3.15%). IR (nujol) cm⁻¹: 3350 (w) (νNH), 1700 (m) (νC=O), 1575 (m) (νC=N), 1440 (m) (νNC=N), 940 (w) (νN-N).

6-Bromo-2-ethylamino-4H-3,1-benzothiazin-4-one (VI): 6-Bromo-3-ethyl-2-thioquinazolin-2,4-(1H,3H)-dione (5.0 g) was refluxed in 75% conc. sulphuric acid at 120-130° on an oil bath for 7 hr. It was cooled and diluted with ice cold water. The product obtained was filtered, washed with 5% sodium bicarbonate solution and finally with distilled water. It was dried and recrystallised from ethanol into shining crystals of 6-bromo-2-ethylamino-4H-3,1-benzothiazin-4-one (VI) in 88% yield, m.p. 228°. (Found: C, 42.2; H, 3.02. Calcd. for C₁₀H₉BrN₂OS; C, 42.11; H, 3.16%). IR (nujol) cm⁻¹: 3300 (w), 1720 (s), 1660 (s), 1390 (s), 1285 (m), 1070 (m), 915 (w), 825 (m).

2'-[3,5-Dibromo-2-aminophenyl]benzimidazole (VII): 3,5-Dibromo anthranilic acid (1 M), *o*-phenylenediamine (1 M) and polyphosphoric acid (16 ml) were refluxed on an oil bath at 235° for 4 hr. The reaction mixture was neutralised with 10% sodium bicarbonate solution. The product was filtered, washed with distilled water and dried. Recrystallisation from alcohol gave the pure product in 40% yield, m.p. 194°. (Found: C, 42.65; H, 2.38. Calcd. for C₁₃H₉Br₂N₃; C, 42.51; H, 2.45%). IR (nujol) cm⁻¹: 3400 (b), 3200 (w), 1620 (m), 1390 (m).

2,4-Dibromo-6-methyl benzimidazo[1,2-*c*]quinazoline (VIII): VII (1 M) was refluxed in glacial acetic acid for 3 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into ice cold water and neutralised with 5% NaHCO₃ solution. The product was then filtered, washed with distilled water, dried and recrystallised from ethanol in 61% yield, m.p. 274°. (Found: C, 46.12; H, 2.19. Calcd. for C₁₅H₉Br₂N₃; C, 46.04; H, 2.30%).

2,4-Dibromo-benzimidazo[1,2-*c*]quinazolin-6(5H)-thione (IX): VII (0.01 M) was refluxed with alcoholic KOH (0.01 M) solution and carbon disulphide (8 ml) for 12 hr. Carbon disulphide was distilled off and the residue neutralised with 5 N hydrochloric acid, filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallised from DMF in 81% yield, m.p. 216°. (Found:

C, 40.98; H, 1.64. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_7Br_2N_3S$; C, 41.08; H, 1.71%. IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3200 (b), 1580 (s), 1420 (s), 1380 (w), 1180 (b), 815 (w).

2,4-Dibromo-6-[N,N-benzyl phenyl carbamoylmethylthio]benzimidazo[1,2-c]quinazoline (XI): IX was dissolved in an alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution. An alcoholic solution of N-benzylchloroacetanilide was added into it dropwise. The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 2-3 hr and left overnight. It was further diluted with distilled water, filtered, washed with distilled water, dried and recrystallised from DMF in 76% yield, m.p. 101°. (Found: C, 54.98; H, 3.02. Calcd. for $C_{29}H_{20}Br_2N_4OS$; C, 55.06; H, 3.17%). IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 1650 (s), 1600 (m), 1500 (m), 1460 (w), 1390 (m).

Bis-[2,4-dibromobenzimidazo[1,2-c]quinazolin-6-yl]disulphide (XI): Saturated iodine solution in potassium iodide was added dropwise to an alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution of IX. The product was washed with a little potassium iodide solution to remove excess iodine and then with distilled water. It was dried and recrystallised from DMF in 84% yield, m.p. 181°. (Found: C, 71.68; H, 2.82. Calcd. for $C_{28}H_{12}Br_4N_6S_2$; C, 71.8; H, 2.99%). IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 1620 (s), 1450 (s), 1230 (w), 760 (m), 530 (vw) (ν S-S).

2,4-Dibromo-6-carboxymethylthio-benzimidazo[1,2-c]quinazoline (XII): IX (1M) was dissolved in minimum sodium hydroxide solution and stirred at room temperature with sodium chloroacetate solution for 1-2 hr and left overnight. It was then neutralised with 5N conc. hydrochloric acid. The product was filtered, washed with distilled water, dried and recrystallised from DMF in 86% yield, m.p. 127°. (Found: C, 40.9; H, 1.79. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_7Br_2N_3O_2S$; C, 41.11; H, 1.93%). IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3250 (w), 1710 (s), 1600 (s), 1440 (s), 760 (m).

2,4-Dibromo-benzimidazo[1,2-c]quinazoline-6(5H)-one (XIII): XIII was obtained by the oxidation of 2,4-dibromo benzimidazo[1,2-c]quinazolin-6(5H)-thione with alkaline $KMnO_4$ by the method of Dave *et al*¹⁰ in 74% yield, m.p. 154°. (Found: C, 40.76; H, 1.68. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_7N_3Br_2O$; C, 40.95; H, 1.84%).

Hydrolysis of 2,4-dibromo-6-(carboxymethylthio)benzimidazo[1,2-c]quinazoline (XII): 5N Hydrochloric acid was added to an alcoholic solution of XII and refluxed for 6-7 hr. Ethanol was distilled off and the reaction mixture was diluted with water,

filtered, washed with distilled water and dried. It was recrystallised from DMF in 79% yield, m.p. 157°. (Found: C, 40.88; H, 1.76. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_7Br_2N_3O$; C, 40.95; H, 1.84%). IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3120 (w), 1720 (m), 1600 (s), 1450 (m), 1220 (m).

Similarly, XIII was also obtained when an alcoholic solution of 2,4-dibromo-6-carboxymethylthio-benzimidazo[1,2-c]quinazoline (XII) was stirred for 24 hr in conc. hydrochloric acid at room temperature, m.p. 163°. (Found: C, 40.82; H, 1.77. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_7N_3Br_2O$; C, 40.95; H, 1.84%).

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